

Enterprise Mobility How technology can benefit transport industry

- By Nigam Shah

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Mobile technologies are driving the transportation and logistics industries towards the impeccable development. Say, for example, there are some companies who calculate the distance defined point to point.

However, it becomes very hard to locate the customer's area if it is located in some city interiors. Also, there is no possibility of any vehicle to have potential of travelling on any type of road. Whether the problem is heavy traffic, cargo restrictions or low bridges, the most logical route might not be the that feasible.

Mobile solutions help to resolve such issues by:

- Determining the optimal route for identifying the traffic conditions
- Diversions related notifications

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- Choosing the ideal route for each shipment while logging the exact distance traveled

With the help of improvised reporting system developed using mobile tracking solutions, the billing cycle from customers to drivers have experienced 8% reduction in cost. That's quite a substantial saving when you consider the cost of fuel, labor, time and others. And when this level of accuracy is achieved, it benefits the overall company and gets reflected in the return on investment (ROI) for their customer base.

What are best mobile applications making a difference in transportation market?

Since, many years' mobile solutions have been into existences in various forms within the transportation industry. Transportation companies are focusing to improve business operations and update the technology implementations for enhanced efficiencies on the road.

Courier company are using mobility to confirm the delivery through a scanner and electronic signature of customer. They can add the real time alert facility via the mobile device for pick-ups en-route, saving fuel and improving customer service and convenience.

Road conditions alert can help delivery fleet drivers to reach the destination on time. This time saving gives opportunity for an extra pickup. Gradually, the stops increases and at the end of year there would be noticeable additional stops. When you calculate the productivity ratio across a global fleet operation, the ROI is fantastic considering no extra vehicles or labor costs were added.

How can transportation companies cope when they go wrong with mobile technology?

It may happen that while deploying new technologies, bumps are there along the way. Initially, drivers would take time to get comfortable with new applications especially those who are strong believers of traditional methods.

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If a fleet driver is not able to grasp the technology implementation they may result in to a corporate liability or legal issues. For example, an accident is possible to occur while the driver sidetrack their focus on device.

The key to successful mobile solutions is to be ready with the solutions to the expected issues.

Real-time training or support for the drivers without leaving the seat, or other endless scenarios. Popular options to effectively remove liability issues around mobile devices involves

- In vehicle crashes,
- Disabling apps like reporting, texting or scanning code when in motion
- Switching device modes once the vehicle stops to safely access information
- Automatically push software and system updates remotely during off-peak times

At Gateway TechnoLabs, our [enterprise mobility](#) wing focuses on accelerating the business from any industry. Our contribution in transportation and logistics industry is remarkable which reflects in Gateway's portfolio. Minimum team of two experts are involved dedicatedly in monitoring and providing supports to 3000 users.

Build a solution for your drivers to keep up the pace between driving and technology. Contact us here to talk and evaluate about being partner in enterprise mobility for transportation and logistics segment.

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